

The fourth side and the area of a inscribed tetragon with numerical example

Harald Schröer

2015

Abstract: We want to derive two unknown formulas and we calculate the fourth side, if 3 sides are given. The assumption is that the midpoint of the circle is in the tetragon.

Key words: Inscribed tetragon - diagonal - side - area - circumradius - angle

We add the areas of the 4 isosceles triangles with the bases a, b, c, d , at which we use the half product of base and height (see figure).

For the area F we obtain:

$$F = \frac{r}{2} \cdot \left(a \cdot \cos \frac{\alpha_m}{2} + b \cdot \cos \frac{\beta_m}{2} + c \cdot \cos \frac{\gamma_m}{2} + d \cdot \cos \frac{\delta_m}{2} \right)$$

With the figure we have:

$$\sin \frac{\alpha_m}{2} = \frac{a}{2r} \quad \sin \frac{\beta_m}{2} = \frac{b}{2r} \quad \sin \frac{\gamma_m}{2} = \frac{c}{2r} \quad \sin \frac{\delta_m}{2} = \frac{d}{2r}$$

With $\sin^2 \varphi + \cos^2 \varphi = 1$ we follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \frac{\alpha_m}{2} &= \frac{\sqrt{4r^2 - a^2}}{2r} & \cos \frac{\beta_m}{2} &= \frac{\sqrt{4r^2 - b^2}}{2r} \\ \cos \frac{\gamma_m}{2} &= \frac{\sqrt{4r^2 - c^2}}{2r} & \cos \frac{\delta_m}{2} &= \frac{\sqrt{4r^2 - d^2}}{2r} \end{aligned}$$

If we insert these expressions in the first area formula, then we yield:

$$F = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(a \cdot \sqrt{4r^2 - a^2} + b \cdot \sqrt{4r^2 - b^2} + c \cdot \sqrt{4r^2 - c^2} + d \cdot \sqrt{4r^2 - d^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Thus we have the area as function from radius and the four sides. Now we will see how we can express one side through the other three sides.

In the inscribed tetragon is the sum of the corresponding angles equal to 180° . Thus we have $\alpha + \gamma = 180^\circ$. Because of the 4 isosceles triangles we recognize:

$$\beta_1 = \alpha_2 \quad \delta_1 = \gamma_2$$

We can conclude:

$$\alpha = \alpha_1 + \beta_1 \quad \gamma = \gamma_1 + \delta_1$$

and we get at last:

$$\alpha_1 + \beta_1 + \gamma_1 + \delta_1 = 180^\circ \quad (2)$$

With the 4 isosceles triangles we follow:

$$\alpha_2 + \beta_2 + \gamma_2 + \delta_2 = 180^\circ \quad (3)$$

With the figure it is:

$$\cos \beta_1 = \frac{a}{2r} \quad \cos \gamma_1 = \frac{b}{2r} \quad \cos \delta_1 = \frac{c}{2r}$$

and with equation (2):

$$\frac{d}{2r} = \cos \alpha_1 = \cos(180^\circ - \beta_1 - \gamma_1 - \delta_1)$$

Thus:

$$d = 2r \cdot \cos \left(180^\circ - \arccos \frac{a}{2r} - \arccos \frac{b}{2r} - \arccos \frac{c}{2r} \right)$$

Thus the determination of the side d with the radius and the sides a, b, c is possible. Because of this, the area is a function of radius and three sides.

With the heights of the triangles perpendicular to the radii we get with the area formula of triangles:

$$F = \frac{r^2}{2} \cdot (\sin \alpha_m + \sin \beta_m + \sin \gamma_m + \sin \delta_m)$$

Because of the isosceles triangles we have $\alpha_m = 180^\circ - 2\alpha_2$. By reason of $\sin(180^\circ - \varphi) = \sin \varphi$ we can follow:

$$\sin \alpha_m = \sin(180^\circ - 2\alpha_2) = \sin 2\alpha_2$$

With this insertion we obtain:

$$F = \frac{r^2}{2} \cdot (\sin 2\alpha_2 + \sin 2\beta_2 + \sin 2\gamma_2 + \sin 2\delta_2) \quad (4)$$

With equation (3) we can determine the fourth angle with three of these angles. The area is a function of radius and three of these angles.

The following assumption is valid: The midpoint of the circle must be in the tetragon. If the assumption is not valid, then we can use a formula at Bartsch [1] chapter 6.5 p.231 for the circumradius. The solve this formula to zero, then we obtain:

$$0 = \frac{(ab + cd)(ac + bd)(bc + ad)}{(s - a)(s - b)(s - c)(s - d)} - 16r^2$$

with $2s = a + b + c + d$.

Wir divide through 16:

$$0 = f(d) = \frac{(ab + cd)(ac + bd)(bc + ad)}{(b + c + d - a)(a + c + d - b)(a + b + d - c)(a + b + c - d)} - r^2$$

To calculate the fourth side we need a numerical method for example Newton's method:

$$d_{n+1} = d_n - \frac{f(d_n)}{f'(d_n)}$$

$f'(d)$ is the function f differentiation with respect to d and expressed at the value d . Now we construct the differentiation with respect to d with quotient rule and general product rule:

$$f'(d) = ((b + c + d - a)(a + c + d - b)(a + b + d - c)(a + b + c - d))^{-2} \cdot \{ [c \cdot (ac + bd)(bc + ad) + (ab + cd) \cdot b \cdot (bc + ad) + (ab + cd)(ac + bd) \cdot a] \cdot (b + c + d - a)(a + c + d - b)(a + b + d - c)(a + b + c - d)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -[(ab + cd)(ac + bd)(bc + ad) \cdot [(a + c + d - b) \\
& \cdot (a + b + d - c)(a + b + c - d) + (b + c + d - a)(a + b + d - c) \\
& \cdot (a + b + c - d) + (b + c + d - a)(a + c + d - b)(a + b + c - d) \\
& - (b + c + d - a)(a + c + d - b)(a + b + d - c)]] \} \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

Now we treat an example with $r=9.1\text{cm}$, $a=17.9\text{cm}$, $b=6.6\text{cm}$ and $c=9.9\text{cm}$. If we calculate with Newton's method and the initial value $d_1=8\text{cm}$, we get finally $d=7.797136\text{cm}$. The midpoint of the exterior circle is not in the inscribed tetragon. We get a second solution with the other formula to $d=13.136439\text{cm}$. In this case the midpoint of the exterior circle is in the inscribed tetragon.

A more general area formula can be found in Bronstein [2] chapter 2.6.1 p. 193:

$$F = \sqrt{(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)(s-d)}$$

We get $F = 83.113353\text{cm}^2$ respectively $F = 121.879077\text{cm}^2$ as area values. The figures are reduced in size:

Further trigonometric problems that can be found scarcely in the literature are at Schröder [3].

References

- [1] Hans-Jochen Bartsch "Taschenbuch mathematischer Formeln"
7.-9.edition 1986 VEB Fachbuchverlag Leipsic
- [2] I.N. Bronstein, K.A. Semendjajew "Taschenbuch der Mathematik" Teubner
Verlagsgesellschaft Leipsic 1985 22.edition
- [3] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft &
Technik Verlag Berlin 2001